

Assamese Saying of Dak With Reference To Agriculture

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Dak is a very well known and age old personality of Assamese society. According to the mythology Dak who was born in lower Assam gave people of Assam some traditional knowledge. He is one of the richest source of oral literature in Assamese. The study aimed to explore the agriculture system prevailing in the villages of Assam. The study concentrates on the Assamese sayings of Dak which is spoken in the Assamese Language. Dak also mentioned about architecture, cooking, folk medicine, life management etc. All these things were scientifically philosophically put forward by Dak for the people of Assam, and he tried to spread it - among the people of Assam. Although at present we are using various innovative techniques in agriculture but we can't deny or forget about the various contributions of Dak in the field of Agriculture. We have selected this topic "Assamese Saying of Dak with reference to Agriculture" to know about the different agricultural contribution of Dak towards Assamese Society

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